

Vibrational Study of Antiparasitic Nifurtimox Agent Combining Harmonic Force Fields with DFT Calculations

Maximiliano A. Iramain ,

Maria V. Castillo

Cátedra de Química General, Instituto de Química Inorgánica, Facultad de Bioquímica, Química y Farmacia, Universidad Nacional de Tucumán, Ayacucho 471, (4000) San Miguel de Tucumán, Tucumán, Argentina

Suggested Citation

Iramain, M.A., Guzzetti, K.A., Manzur, M.E., Castillo, M.V., & Brandán, S.A. (2024). Vibrational Study of Antiparasitic Nifurtimox Agent Combining Harmonic Force Fields with DFT Calculations. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 711-732. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).63](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).63)

Abstract:

A theoretical study has been performed on the anti-chagasic nifurtimox agent (NFX), by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations in the gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solution to characterize the structures and vibrational spectra. The most stable conformer predicted by calculations is in agreement with the experimental reported by X-ray diffraction with a higher solvation energy in aqueous solution (-134.81 kJ/mol) than in DMSO solution (-90.71 kJ/mol). A higher dipole moment and contraction of volume is predicted in aqueous solution probably due to the presence of strongly acceptors SO₂ and NO₂ groups of H bonds associated to the higher permittivity of water. Nucleophilic sites on the SO₂ and

NO₂ groups are revealed by the mapped MEP surfaces with a higher energy value in water. The higher stability of NFX in solution is supported by NBO calculations while the frontier orbitals show that NFX is most reactive in both solutions than in the gas phase. Here, complete vibrational assignments of FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra in the three media have been performed by using the normal internal coordinates, the scaled mechanical force field (SQMFF) methodology and the Molvib program. The predicted NMR and UV-vis spectra show good concordances with the corresponding experimental ones.

Keywords: *Nifurtimox; DFT calculations; Molecular structure, Vibrational spectra; Force Fields.*

Introduction

Benzimidazoles derivatives have emerged as interesting antiparasitic drugs such as, nifurtimox, benznidazole, metronidazole, and meglazine to treat chronic chagas disease because they present activity against *Trypanosoma cruzi* (Moroni, et al., 2023; Chaves, et al., 2018; Bezerra, et al., 2014; Brain-Isasi, et al., 2008; Soriano-Correa, Raya, & Esquivé, 2008; Lang, et al., 2022; Maldonado, et al., 2021; Sperandeo, et al., 2005; Terra Martins, et al., 2010; Salah, Belaidi, & Melkemi, 2016; Bulffer, Castro, & Fanelli, 2011; Nuñez-Vergara, et al., 1997;

Foces-Foces, et al., 1988). Interactions between those four antiparasitic drugs with human serum albumin (HSA) have been evaluated by UV-Vis, circular dichroism (CD), steady state, time-resolved, synchronous and 3D fluorescence and theoretical calculations (Chaves, et al., 2018). The electronic structure and physicochemical properties of nifurtimox analogues have been theoretically reported while the experimental structure was determined by using x-ray diffraction by Foces-Foces et al. (1988). Recently, Moroni et al have published solid state properties, preparation, analytical characterization, and stability of an amorphous

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

phase of nifurtimox by using powder X-ray diffraction, NMR, Mid- and near- infrared spectroscopy and thermal studies (Moroni, et al., 2023). In that study, only some important IR bands have been assigned. Lang et al reported structural and mechanistic investigation of the unusual metabolism of nifurtimox (Lang, et al., 2022) while Bulffer et al reported the UV methodology for the determination of anti-Chagasics Nifurtimox and Benznidazole in blood (Bulffer, Castro, & Fanelli, 2011). The identification of nifurtimox by using vibrational spectroscopy is very important to recognise the presence of bands related nitro group because exist biological evidences of nitro radical anion formation from nifurtimox in trypanosoma cruzi (Nuñez-Vergara, et al., 1997). The IUPAC name of nifurtimox is (*E*)-*N*-(3-methyl-1,1-dioxo-1,4-thiazinan-4-yl)-1-(5-nitrofur-2-yl)methanimine while its molecular structure and definition of rings is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Molecular Structure of Nifurtimox with Definition of Rings

In a previous study, we reported structural and vibrational characterization of benznidazole by using force fields and internal coordinates because these studies are essential for its identification by using the infrared and Raman spectra (Iramain, et al., 2023). In this work, we have characterized the structures and vibrational spectra of nifurtimox because, so far, the complete assignments of infrared and Raman spectra are not reported yet. The vibrational spectroscopy is a very quick and useful technique to identify any species in different phases while when these spectra are combined with

theoretical calculations all the bands observed in the spectra can be easily assigned with aid of the scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMFF) methodology (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Besides, the use of normal internal coordinates and scaling factors performs complete and reliable assignments. In this context, the aims of this work are to optimize the initial structure of nifurtimox in the gas phase and aqueous and DMSO solutions by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations in order to compute the structural, electronic, topological and vibrational properties (Becke, 1988; Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988; Dennington, Keith, & Millam, 2019; Frisch, et al., 2019; Miertuš, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981). Then, the predicted infrared, Raman, ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR, ultraviolet and electronic circular dichroism (ECD) spectra at the same level of theory are compared with the corresponding experimental ones to see the correlations among them. After that, the complete vibrational assignments of nifurtimox and the scaled force constants are reported. The results obtained for this species are compared with obtained for benznidazole (Iramain, et al., 2023).

Methodology Employed

The experimental CIF file reported by Foces-Foces et al. (1988) was taken as initial theoretical structure of nifurtimox (NFX) and, then, the optimizations in the gas phase and aqueous and DMSO solutions by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method were performed with the Gaussian 16 program (Becke, 1988; Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988; Dennington, Keith, & Millam, 2019; Frisch, et al., 2019). Here, two solvents with different permittivity values (water, $\epsilon=78.3553$ and DMSO, $\epsilon=46.826$) have been used to investigate the effect of solvent on properties of NFX (Miertuš, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981; Tomasi, & Persico, 1994; Marenich, Cramer, & Truhlar, 2009). After that, the potential energy surfaces (PES) were studied for variations of the dihedral C-C-C-N, C-C-N-N, C-N-N-C and N-C-C-C angles by using the same level of theory. Hence, five stable conformations have been found in PES and,

where C1 corresponds to the theoretical most stable with the global minimum, as shown in Fig. 2. The experimental and theoretical most stable structures of NFX in gas phase by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory are presented in Fig. 3. NBO calculations (Glendening, et al., 1996) were also performed to calculate the bond orders, expressed as Wiberg indexes, acceptor-donor interactions energies, atomic natural populations (NPA), MK (Merz-Kollman) charges and the molecular electrostatic potentials (MEP) while the AIM 2000 program was used to compute the

topological properties of NFX at the same level of theory (Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). Then, the harmonic force fields were also computed by using normal internal coordinates and transferable scaling factors with the SQMFF methodology and the Molvib program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). The vibrational assignments have been performed using comparisons between the predicted IR and Raman with the experimental ones and Potential Energy Distribution (PED) contributions $\geq 10\%$.

Figure 2. Stable Conformations Obtained by Means of the Potential Energy Surfaces (PES) for Variations of the Dihedral C-C-C-N, C-C-N-N, C-N-N-C and N-C-C-C Angles of Nifurtimox in Gas Phase by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Figure 3. Molecular Theoretical Structures of Nifurtimok with the Atoms Numbering

The differences between their frontier orbitals, known as gap, and some global descriptors were predicted to know their reactivities and behaviours in the different media (Pearson, 1986; Parr, Szentpály, & Liu, 1999). Volumes

variations have been calculated with the Moldraw program (Ugliengo, 1998). The NMR and electronic spectra have been predicted by using respectively the GIOA method and the Gaussian 16 program (Frisch, et al., 2019;

Ditchfield, 1974). The Raman spectra predicted in activity have been transformed in intensities (Keresztury, et al., 1993).

Results and Discussion

Optimizations in Different Media

The results obtained from the optimization of NFX in the different media can be seen in Table 1. Calculated uncorrected (E) and corrected (E_{ZPVE}) total energies, dipole moments, volumes and its variations by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method are presented in that table.

Table 1. Calculated Total Energies (E), Dipole Moments (μ) and Volumes (V) of (E)-N-(3-methyl-1,1-dioxo-1,4-thiazinan-4-yl)-1-(5-nitrofur-2-yl)methanimine (Nifurtimox) in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method					
Medium	E (Hartrees)	E_{ZPVE}	μ (D)	V (\AA^3)	ΔV (\AA^3)
Gas Phase	-1327.521	-1327.280	5.79	265.3	0.8
DMSO	-1327.559	-1327.318	8.60	266.1	
Water	-1327.561	-1327.320	10.39	263.9	-1.4

Evaluating the results, it is observed that the dipole moment is higher in water than in gas phase and DMSO solution while the volume is lower in water. Thus, a contraction of V is observed in water different from the other media. Here, the presence of groups strongly acceptor of H bonds, such as SO_2 and NO_2 probably justify the higher μ and $< V$ in water due to its higher permittivity value (78.3553). When the orientations and directions of μ vectors of NFX in the different media are analysed from Figure 4, we observed slight variations in the orientations and directions of μ although the three vectors are located almost parallel to $\text{N8}=\text{C15}$ bonds from N8 to CH_3

group of methylthiomorpholine ring but with different orientations. Hence, the influence of solvents on μ and V are evident. Taking into account the contraction of V predicted for NFT in water, the solvation energies in DMSO and water have been predicted at the same level of theory. Thus, Table 2 shows the corrected solvation energy by zero point vibrational energy ($ZPVE$) (ΔG_{ZPVE}) and by non-electrostatic terms (ΔG_c) with the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method. ΔG_{ne} represents the energy due to the non-electrostatic terms computed from the optimizations of NFT in the different solvents by using the PCM method.

Figure 4. Orientations and Directions of Dipole Moment Vectors of Nifurtimox in Gas Phase, DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Table 2. Corrected and Uncorrected Solvation Energies by the Total Non-Electrostatic Terms for (E)-N-(3-methyl-1,1-dioxo-1,4-thiazinan-4-yl)-1-(5-nitrofur-2-yl)methanimine (Nifurtimox) DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Solvation energy (kJ/mol)			
Solvent	$\Delta G_{(ZPVE)}$	ΔG_{ne}	ΔG_e
DMSO	-99.67	-8.90	-90.71
Water	-104.92	29.89	-134.81

Regarding, the solvation energy values predicted by calculations we observed the most negative and higher solvation energy for NFT in water. Then, the presence of strongly acceptors groups of H bonds (SO₂ and NO₂) and the higher μ and $< V$ in water could be associated to the higher permittivity of water (78.3553). Besides, the strong deactivating NO₂ group tend to withdraw electron density to the nitrofur ring.

The correlations between the experimental structure determined by X-ray diffraction by Foces-Foces et al. (1988) and the theoretical optimized in both media by B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations are fundamental to perform the vibrational analyses. For these reasons, the root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Calculated Geometrical Parameters of (E)-N-(3-methyl-1,1-dioxo-1,4-thiazinan-4-yl)-1-(5-nitrofur-2-yl)methanimine (Nifurtimox) in Gas Phase, DMSO and Aqueous Solutions at B3LYP /6-311G Level of Theory with the Corresponding Experimental Ones**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a				Exp ^b
	Gas phase	DMSO	Water	
Bond lengths (Å)				
S1=O2	1.471	1.476	1.484	
S1=O3	1.465	1.479	1.481	
S1-C11	1.822	1.815	1.810	1.765
C11-C10	1.543	1.543	1.543	1.534
C10-N7	1.479	1.478	1.480	1.473
S1-C12	1.824	1.816	1.810	1.770
C12-C13	1.537	1.535	1.534	1.532
C13-N7	1.466	1.466	1.468	1.457
N7-N8	1.344	1.327	1.328	1.339
N8=C15	1.289	1.297	1.298	1.283
C15-C16	1.443	1.435	1.430	
C16=C17	1.379	1.388	1.390	1.366
C17-C18	1.414	1.404	1.399	1.401
C18=C19	1.368	1.376	1.379	1.344
C19-N9	1.425	1.400	1.384	1.411
N9-O5	1.232	1.243	1.249	1.211
N9-O6	1.227	1.239	1.247	1.233
C19-O4	1.352	1.358	1.364	1.355
O4-C16	1.365	1.363	1.366	1.373
RMSD^b	0.022	0.021	0.021	
Bond angles (°)				
O2S1C11	107.4	108.5	108.6	108.0
O3S1C11	109.5	109.4	109.7	110.2
C12S1O3	109.2	109.6	109.7	110.0
O2S1C12	107.2	108.4	108.6	108.3
O2S1O3	120.6	118.0	116.9	117.4
S1C11C10	111.3	111.8	111.8	111.2

S1C12C13	109.8	110.3	110.0	109.6
C12S1C11	101.1	101.7	102.1	101.7
C11C10C14	111.5	110.7	110.1	
C14C10N7	112.5	113.2	113.5	
C11C10N7	110.4	110.0	110.1	110.0
C10N7N8	114.1	116.0	115.5	113.7
N7N8C15	122.6	122.9	122.2	123.2
C10N7C13	114.2	114.7	114.1	114.9
C13N7N8	121.7	123.4	122.7	122.9
N8C15C16	119.2	117.8	118.0	115.2
C15C16C17	134.8	134.1	134.4	107.1
C16C17C18	106.6	106.8	106.9	107.1
C17C18C19	105.5	105.8	105.9	105.6
C18C19N9	130.8	131.1	131.4	130.9
C19N9O5	116.1	117.2	117.9	116.6
O6N9O5	125.7	123.9	122.8	123.6
C19N9O6	118.3	119.0	119.1	119.5
N9C19O4	111.5	117.7	117.4	116.6
N7C13C12	112.4	112.0	112.2	112.2
C16O4C19	106.4	106.5	106.2	105.0
O4C19C18	111.5	111.2	111.1	112.5
C17C16O4	109.8	109.8	109.7	109.8
C15C16O4	115.4	116.1	115.8	116.9
RMSD^b	0.712	0.529	0.429	
Dihedral angles (°)				
O2S1C11C10	-61.7	-65.0	-65.9	
O3S1C11C10	165.7	165.0	165.0	170.0
S1C11C10C14	174.7	175.7	175.9	
S1C11C10N7	-59.4	-58.4	-58.0	-59.5
S1C12C13N7	59.9	59.0	59.2	59.5
C10C11S1O2	-61.7	-64.9	-65.9	-60.6
C10C11S1C12	50.4	49.2	48.6	53.3
C14C10N7N8	45.7	37.2	40.1	
C10N7N8C15	162.3	164.3	162.2	165.4
C11C10N7C13	66.7	66.8	66.7	64.1
N7N8C15C16	175.9	175.6	176.5	173.6
N8C15C16C17	-1.6	-1.1	-0.3	
N8C15C16O4	178.2	179.1	179.2	184.2
O4C19N9O6	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-2.4
C11S1C12C13	-49.6	-48.4	-48.1	-52.0
C10N7C13C12	-68.0	-68.2	-68.6	-65.3
C13N7N8C15	19.2	12.7	14.2	18.9
C14C10N7C13	-168.0	-168.7	-169.0	188.5
RMSD^b	1.78	2.24	2.59	

Source: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Foces-Foces, et al., 1988.

Note: RMSD in bold letters

Examining the results of the table, in general, very good concordances in the RMSD values are observed for bond lengths (0.022-0.021 Å) and angles (0.712-0.429 °), however, for the dihedral angles the RMSD values slightly increase to 2.59-1.78 °. Thus, the higher discrepancies in the

optimized structures in the three media are observed in the signs of dihedral C14-C10-N7-C13 angles. Therefore, very good correlations suggest evidently that the three structures can be considered in the vibrational analyses.

Atomic Charges, MEP and BO Studies

Due to the presence of strongly acceptors groups of H bonds (SO₂ and NO₂), three types of atomic charges, the atomic natural populations (NPA) and Merz-Kollman (MK) and Mulliken charges have been studied together with the molecular electrostatic potential (MEP)

and bond orders (BO) (Glendening, et al., 1996; Besler, Merz, & Kollman, 1990). Table 4 shows those types of charges calculated on the S, O, N and C15 and H30 atoms of NFX in the three media by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method. Here, only the more important variations were considered.

Table 4. Atomic Charges (in a.u.) for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Atoms	B3LYP /6-311++G**								
	GAS			DMSO			Water		
	MK	Mulliken	NPA	MK	Mulliken	NPA	MK	Mulliken	NPA
S 1	0.999	0.670	2.039	0.995	0.681	2.029	1.010	0.724	2.030
O 2	-0.556	-0.198	-0.933	-0.616	-0.266	-0.964	-0.622	-0.284	-0.966
O 3	-0.556	-0.090	-0.910	-0.631	-0.212	-0.955	-0.632	-0.233	-0.956
O 4	-0.269	-0.042	-0.437	-0.305	-0.075	-0.447	-0.310	-0.069	-0.445
O 5	-0.460	-0.007	-0.394	-0.534	-0.065	-0.448	-0.542	-0.089	-0.457
O 6	-0.420	-0.016	-0.372	-0.500	-0.089	-0.434	-0.510	-0.117	-0.446
N 7	-0.114	0.663	-0.296	-0.098	0.676	-0.265	-0.076	0.652	-0.267
N 8	-0.359	-0.239	-0.225	-0.376	-0.261	-0.211	-0.375	-0.217	-0.201
N 9	0.680	-0.299	0.450	0.696	-0.323	0.438	0.693	-0.296	0.434
C 15	0.183	-0.298	-0.044	0.088	-0.356	-0.069	0.118	-0.302	-0.063
H 30	0.087	0.131	0.182	0.137	0.192	0.209	0.120	0.158	0.200

Analysing deeply the results we observed that the behaviours of MK and NPA charges on the S1, O2, O3, O4, O5, O6, N7, N8 and N9 atoms in the three media are similar between them but very different to the Mulliken charges although with some differences. Thus, positive Mulliken charges on N7 are observed while the other charges show negative values. Besides, there are not differences among the values in DMSO and water while in the gas phase the Mulliken charges on O3 and O5 present less negative values. In addition, slight differences are observed in the NPA charges on O4, O5, O6, N7 and N8 while the MK charges on O4 and N7 have less negative values. These differences on charges of O and N atoms belonging to SO₂ and NO₂ groups and to the two rings reveal the importance of these atoms in the properties of NFX. Note that the MK charges on C15 of C15-H30 bond show positive values while the other two charges negative values. In reference to the H atoms, the H30 show the lower values because

this atom is the most labile in the different media.

The molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) on the S, O, N and C15 and H30 atoms of NFX in the three media are presented in Table 5 by using the same level of theory while the mapped MEP surfaces for NFX are observed in Figure 5. The evaluations of the MEP values only show differences due to their electronegativities, hence, the trend is S > O > N > C > H (Besler, Merz, & Kollman, 1990). Then, the red colours are observed on the O atoms of SO₂ and NO₂ groups while the blue colours on the H atoms belonging to the C-H groups of nitrofurane and methylthiomorpholine rings. Then, the nucleophilic sites are characterized by red colours while the electrophilic sites by blue colours. A very important detail is the increase in the E value in aqueous solution, as expected due to > μ value. Thus, the E value increase from 0.0518 a.u. in gas phase to 0.076 a.u. in water.

Table 5. Calculated Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) (a. u.) for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Atoms	B3LYP /6-311++G**		
	Gas	DMSO	Water
S 1	-59.023	-59.017	-59.017
O 2	-22.371	-22.380	-22.383
O 3	-22.371	-22.385	-22.387
O 4	-22.258	-22.264	-22.258
O 5	-22.342	-22.376	-22.379
O 6	-22.340	-22.377	-22.381
N 7	-18.303	-18.269	-18.271
N 8	-18.330	-18.306	-18.301
N 9	-18.147	-18.174	-18.175
C 15	-14.702	-14.687	-14.682
H 30	-1.052	-1.021	-1.025

Figure 5. Calculated Electrostatic Potential Surfaces on the Molecular Surface of the Most Stable Conformer of NFX in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions. B3LYP/6-311++G. Isodensity Value of 0.005**

The inert sites characterized by green colours are practically not observed on the mapped MEP surfaces and, for these reasons, there are two reactive regions located on the nitrofurane and methylthiomorpholine rings.

In relation to the bond orders (BO) for NFX in the three media the values are summarized in Table 6. Evaluating, the results we observed that

the S atoms in the different media show the higher values, in particular in gas phase while the lower value in water. Such difference is associated to increase of two S=O bonds in aqueous solution, as observed from Table 3. The elongation of bonds in solution produces a decrease in bond orders, particularly in aqueous solution.

Table 6. Calculated Bond Orders Expressed, as Wiberg Indexes by Atoms, for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP /6-311++G**			
Atoms	Gas	DMSO	Water
S 1	4.234	4.205	4.202
O 2	1.616	1.566	1.559
O 3	1.646	1.576	1.571
O 4	2.307	2.291	2.291
O 5	2.013	1.951	1.936
O 6	2.037	1.969	1.950
N 7	3.406	3.474	3.463
N 8	3.139	3.138	3.140
N 9	3.972	3.963	3.960
C 15	3.944	3.932	3.936
H 30	0.972	0.961	0.965

Hydration in water causes a diminishing in the BO of O atoms although the BO of N8 decrease slightly in DMSO and remain practically constant in gas phase and aqueous solution probably due to that N8=C15 bond is linked to most labile C15-H30 bond, as supported by the decreasing in the MEP in aqueous solution (See Table 5). These studies show the effects of most important groups and rings on the atomic charges, MEP and bond orders revealing higher variations of these properties in water due to its higher solvation energy in this medium.

Stabilities Studies by NBO and AIM Calculations

In this section, the donor-acceptor energy interactions and the topological properties are analysed for NFX in the three media by using the NBO and AIM calculations because these parameters predict the stabilities in the different media (Glendening, et al., 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). This way, interactions are investigated with the

NBO program (Glendening, et al., 1996) while the intra-molecular interactions can be easily explained by using the Bader' theory (Bader, 1990) and the AIM 2000 program (Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). Table 7 shows the second order perturbation theory analysis of Fock matrix in NBO Basis computed with NBO calculations. The results show five different $\Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$, $\Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow LP}$, $\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$, $\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$ and $\Delta E_{\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*}$ delocalizations from π orbitals and lone pairs of the O and N atoms (LP) toward different π or σ (S-C, S-O, C-C, O-N, N-C) orbitals. Thus, we see that the $\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$ interactions also named $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ present high values in the three media having in the gas phase the higher values. Note that the $\pi O6-N9 \rightarrow LP(3)O5$ interaction is predicted only in the gas phase When the total donor-acceptor energy interactions are computed, it is observed that in DMSO the value is higher than in gas phase and aqueous solution. Hence, NFX in DMSO is most stable than gas and aqueous solution while in water has > stability than in the gas phase.

Table 7. Main Delocalization Energy (in kJ/mol) for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP /6-311++G**a			
Delocalization	Gas	DMSO	Water
$\pi N8-C15 \rightarrow \pi^* C16-C17$	49.28	57.31	57.89
$\pi C16-C17 \rightarrow \pi^* N8-C15$	60.94	58.69	60.02
$\pi C16-C17 \rightarrow \pi^* C18-C19$	85.44	100.19	103.16
$\pi C18-C19 \rightarrow \pi^* O6-N9$	107.43	150.31	165.36

$\pi C18-C19 \rightarrow \pi^* C16-C17$	59.31	57.93	59.77
$\Sigma \Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$	362.40	424.43	446.20
$\pi O6-N9 \rightarrow LP(3)O5$	46.77		
$\Sigma \Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow LP}$	46.77		
$LP(3) O3 \rightarrow \pi^* S1-O2$	91.04	87.82	86.60
$LP(2) O2 \rightarrow \pi^* S1-C11$	57.10	52.25	51.91
$LP(2) O2 \rightarrow \pi^* S1-C12$	56.22	52.58	51.45
$LP(2) O3 \rightarrow \pi^* S1-C11$	60.53	53.04	52.25
$LP(2) O3 \rightarrow \pi^* S1-C12$	59.02	53.38	52.96
$LP(2) O5 \rightarrow \pi^* O6-N9$	76.95	75.74	73.21
$LP(2) O5 \rightarrow \pi^* N9-C19$	44.98	-	-
$LP(2) O6 \rightarrow \pi^* O5-N9$	78.17	76.12	79.51
$LP(2) O6 \rightarrow \pi N9-C19$	52.17	43.76	74.09
$LP(2) O4 \rightarrow \pi^* C16-C17$	118.92	119.67	118.58
$LP(2) O4 \rightarrow \pi^* C18-C19$	112.99	102.33	100.32
$LP(3) O2 \rightarrow \pi^* S1-O3$	86.61	85.48	84.22
$LP(1) N7 \rightarrow \pi^* N8-C15$	154.83	186.93	177.19
$LP(3) O5 \rightarrow \pi^* O6-N9$	647.94	597.41	584.48
$\Sigma \Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$	1697.83	1586.51	1586.76
$LP(1) N8 \rightarrow \sigma^* N7-C13$	45.44	49.45	48.90
$LP(1) N8 \rightarrow \sigma^* C15-H30$	46.15	42.43	42.92
$\Sigma \Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	91.59	91.88	91.82
$\pi^* O6-N9 \rightarrow \pi^* C18-C19$	87.03	95.81	103.91
$\pi^* N8-C15 \rightarrow \pi^* C16-C17$	554.02	855.14	751.06
$\Sigma \Delta E_{\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*}$	641.05	950.95	854.97
$\Sigma TOTAL$	2840.09	3053.77	2979.75

Source: ^aThis work

The stabilities of NFX in the three media were also evaluated with the topological properties according to the Bader' theory (Bader, 1990) and the AIM 2000 program (Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). Then, the electron density distribution, $\rho(r)$, the values of the Laplacian, $\nabla^2\rho(r)$, the eigenvalues ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$) of the Hessian matrix and the λ_1/λ_3 ratio in the

bond critical points (BCPs) and ring critical points (RCPs) have been calculated and the results can be seen in Table 8. This way, for high values of $\rho(r)$ and $\nabla^2\rho(r)$, the ratio $\lambda_1/\lambda_3 > 1$ and $\nabla^2\rho(r) < 0$ the interaction is covalent (shared interaction) while when $\lambda_1/\lambda_3 < 1$ and $\nabla^2\rho(r) > 0$ (closed-shell interaction) the interaction is ionic or highly polar covalent.

Table 8. Analysis of the Topological Properties for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Parameter [#]	B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a			
	Gas Phase			
	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	C13-H25...H30-C15
$\rho(r)$	0.0157	0.0537	0.0139	0.0139
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.092	0.3604	0.0664	0.0664
λ_1	-0.0103	-0.0581	-0.0116	-0.0116
λ_2	0.0491	0.2068	0.0073	0.0073
λ_3	0.0532	0.2119	0.0709	0.0709

$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1936	0.2742	0.1636	0.1636
Distances				2.0150
DMSO				
Parameter [#]	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	C13-H25...H30-C15
$\rho(\tau)$	0.0157	0.0539	0.0137	0.0138
$\nabla^2\rho(\tau)$	0.0920	0.3620	0.0644	0.0568
λ_1	-0.0103	-0.0583	-0.0117	-0.0130
λ_2	0.0491	0.2074	0.0051	-0.0042
λ_3	0.0532	0.2129	0.0710	0.0740
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1936	0.2738	0.1645	0.1757
Distances				2.7564
Aqueous Solution				
Parameter [#]	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	C13-H25...H30-C15
$\rho(\tau)$	0.0157	0.0529	0.0142	0.0146
$\nabla^2\rho(\tau)$	0.9240	0.3564	0.0689	0.5812
λ_1	-0.0103	-0.0569	-0.0122	-0.0142
λ_2	0.0491	0.2043	0.0080	-0.0062
λ_3	0.0538	0.2086	0.0730	0.0786
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.0191	0.2727	0.1671	0.1806
Distances				1.988

Source: ^aThis work, [#]Parameters in a.u.

Details of the molecular models for NFX in gas phase and DMSO and aqueous solutions are shown in Fig. 6. The results show the formation of an H bond in the different media. RCP1 and RCP2 correspond respectively to

methylthiomorpholine R1 and nitrofuran R2 rings of Fig. 1 while RCPN is the new RCP in blue colours (Fig. 6) due to the formation of H bonds.

Figure 6. Details of the Molecular Model for NFX in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Levels of Theory

Table 8 show that the new H bond present higher topological properties in water because the distance between the H25-H30 is 1.988 Å different from gas phase (2.015 Å) and DMSO (2.7564 Å). These results confirm the lability of H30, as supported by the less negative MEP values and the donor H bond characteristic of C15-H30 bond.

Frontier Orbitals and Global Descriptors

The prediction of reactivities and behaviours of NFX in the three media is important taking into account its activity as antiparasitic drug (Maldonado, et al., 2021; Salah, Belaidi, & Melkemi, 2016; Bulffer, Castro, & Fanelli, 2011; Nuñez-Vergara, et al., 1997). Hence, the gap values and some descriptors are calculated from

the frontier orbitals (Pearson, 1986; Parr, Szentpály, & Liu, 1999). Thus, calculated HOMO and LUMO, gap, chemical potential (μ), electronegativity (χ), global hardness (η), global softness (S) and global electrophilicity index (ω) for NFX are presented in Table 9 by using the 6-311++G** basis set compared with benznidazole (BEN), other important drug with the same activity (Iramain, et al., 2023). The evaluation of results show that NFX in DMSO (3.009 eV) and aqueous (3.019 eV) solutions present lower gap values and, for these reasons, the NFX drug is most reactive in both solutions than in the gas phase (3.495 eV), although a higher reactivity is observed in DMSO than water.

Table 8. Calculated HOMO and LUMO Orbitals, Energy Band Gap, Chemical Potential (μ), Electronegativity (χ), Global Hardness (η), Global Softness (S) and Global Electrophilicity Index (ω) for NFX in Gas Phase, DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the 6-311++G Level of Theory**

B3LYP /6-311G** Method ^a					
Orbital (eV)	Nifurtimox			Benznidazole ^b	
	Gas	DMSO	Water	Gas	Ethanol
HOMO (75)	-6.606	-5.922	-0.231	-7.1044	-6.8816
LUMO (76)	-3.111	-2.913	-0.120	-3.2288	-3.2008
GAP	3.495	3.009	3.019	3.8756	3.6808
Descriptors					
χ	4.858	4.417	4.770	-1.9378	-1.8404
μ	-4.858	-4.417	-4.770	-5.1666	-5.0412
η	3.302	2.960	3.140	1.9438	1.8404
S	0.151	0.168	0.159	0.2572	0.2717
ω	3.573	3.294	3.624	6.8662	6.9043

Note: $\chi = - [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\mu = [E(\text{LUMO}) + E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\eta = [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $S = 1/2\eta$; $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$;

Source: ^aThis work; ^bFrom Iramain, et al., 2023.

The higher reactivities of NFX in DMSO and aqueous solutions are in agreement with the lower stabilization energies observed in these two media by NBO calculations. The comparisons with BEN show that this drug is most reactive in ethanol solution, however, the higher gap value for BEN in both media implies lower reactivities in the two media than NFX. The analyses of descriptors reveal that the higher reactivity observed for NFX in DMSO is related

to $\langle \chi < \mu < \eta < \omega \rangle S$ while for BEN in ethanol the higher reactivity is associated with its $\langle \chi < \mu < \eta \rangle \omega > S$.

NMR Study

B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations have evidenced that the most stable conformer of NFX is in concordance with the experimental structure reported by Foces-Foces et al in the solid phase (Foces-Foces, et al., 1988). Here, the

structure of NFX is evaluated in DMSO and aqueous solutions to know the correlations between the predicted ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectra and the corresponding experimental ones reported by Moroni et al. (2023) by using the RMSD values. Hence, Tables 9 and 10 show respectively the comparisons of ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR chemical shifts δ expressed in ppm. Evaluating the results of Table 9, we observed a very good concordance for the H atoms in both solvents with a RMSD values of 0.15/0.14 ppm. Higher differences are observed in the H30 atoms because this atom belong to C15-H30 bond which act as donor H bonds in the two media. If now are compared the C atoms, it is observed a slight higher RMSD values showing a better correlation in water (7.5 ppm), as compared in DMSO solution (7.7 ppm).

Table 9. Observed ^1H -NMR Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for NFX in CDCl_3 and Calculated in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a			
Atoms	DMSO	Water	Exp.
H32	7.7	7.8	7.7
H30	7.4	7.4	7.7
H31	6.9	7.0	6.8
H25	4.3	4.3	3.7
H20	3.9	4.0	4.2
H26	3.5	3.5	3.7
H24	3.1	3.2	2.8
H22	2.9	3.0	4.1
H21	2.8	2.8	4.1
H23	2.8	2.8	2.8
H27	1.1	1.6	1.4
H28	1.5	1.5	1.4
H29	1.1	1.1	1.4
RMSD	0.15	0.14	

Source: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref. to TMS.

This study shows that the optimized structures in DMSO and aqueous solution are in agreement with the experimental reported and, hence, the optimized structures in the gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solutions can be used to perform the vibrational study.

Table 10. Observed ^{13}C -NMR Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for NFX in CDCl_3 and Calculated in Gas Phase and DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a		
	DMSO	Water	Exp.
C16	167.4	169.3	154.9
C19	157.4	157.2	150.7
C18	126.5	127.3	115.6
C15	123.9	125.7	125.2
C17	112.4	113.1	110.2
C11	66.8	66.4	55.4
C10	63.0	63.2	56.9
C12	56.1	54.8	45.6
C13	44.2	44.5	43.5
C14	17.6	17.6	16.9
RMSD	7.7	7.5	

Source: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref. to TMS.

Vibrational Analysis

Here, the most stable conformer of NFX was considered because this structure corresponds to the experimental reported by Foces-Foces et al (Foces-Foces, et al., 1988). The experimental infrared of NFX in the solid phase taken from Bedogni, et al., (2023) is compared in Figures 7 with the corresponding predicted for NFX in the gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solutions. Due to the 32 atoms present in NFX, a total de 90 vibration normal modes are expected. All these modes present activities in both IR and Raman spectra.

The SQMFF methodology and B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations were used to calculate the harmonic force fields together with the normal internal coordinates, transferable scaling factors and the Molvib program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Here, local C_{2v} symmetries were considered for both NO_2 and SO_2 groups but planar for the former while tetrahedral for the second one, as reported for species containing these groups (Iramain, et al., 2023; Castillo, et al., 2017). The vibrational assignments for NFX in the three media have been performed considering potential energy distribution (PED) $\geq 10\%$. Thus, in Table 11 are presented the observed and calculated wavenumbers together with the

assignments for NFX in the three different media. Then, brief discussions of some assignments are shown by regions.

Figure 7. Experimental Infrared Spectrum for NFX in the Solid Phase (Bedogni, et al., 2023) Compared with the Predicted in Gas Phase, DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Assignments

4000-2000 cm⁻¹ region. The two C-H stretching modes of nitrofuran ring of NFX in the three media are assigned at higher wavenumbers than the C15-H30 stretching modes while the antisymmetric and symmetric modes expected for the CH₂ and CH₃ groups are associated to the IR bands between 3015 and 2921 cm⁻¹ because they are predicted by calculations in this region (Iramain, et al., 2023; Castillo, et al., 2017; Romani, Márquez, & Brandán, 2023; Brizuela, et al., 2014). Note that the same assignments are observed in the three media with some differences in the intensities and positions, as observed from Fig.7.

2000-1000 cm⁻¹ region. In this region are expected the antisymmetric and symmetric modes of NO₂ and SO₂ groups and, stretching modes of double and partial N-C, C-C bonds together with the in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes of CH groups, the deformation, rocking and wagging modes of CH₂ and CH₃ groups (Iramain, et al., 2023; Castillo, et al., 2017; Romani, Márquez, & Brandán, 2023; Brizuela, et al., 2014). Thus, IR band at 1560 cm⁻¹ is assigned to N8=C15, C18=C19 and C16=C17 stretching modes.

Table 11. Observed and Calculated Wavenumbers (cm-1) and Assignments for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase, DMSO and Aqueous Solutions by Using Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Exp ^c	B3LYP/6-311++G** method ^a					
	Gas phase		DMSO Solution		Aqueous Solution	
IR	SQM ^b	Assignments ^a	SQM ^b	Assignments ^a	SQM ^b	Assignments ^a
	3141	vC18-H32	3136	vC18-H32	3138	vC18-H32
3127w	3128	vC17-H31	3125	vC17-H31	3128	vC17-H31
	3006	v _a CH ₂ (C12)	3015	v _a CH ₂ (C13)	3024	v _a CH ₂ (C13)
	3003	v _a CH ₃	3011	v _a CH ₂ (C12)	3019	v _a CH ₂ (C12)
	2999	v _a CH ₂ (C11)	3007	v _a CH ₂ (C11)	3013	v _a CH ₂ (C11)
	2989	vC15-H30	3003	vC15-H30	3012	vC15-H30
2987w	2984	v _a CH ₃	2996	v _a CH ₃	3001	v _a CH ₃
	2981	v _a CH ₂ (C13)	2982	v _a CH ₃	2988	v _a CH ₃
	2947	v _s CH ₂ C13)	2958	v _s CH ₂ C13)	2970	v _s CH ₂ C13)
	2946	v _s CH ₂ (C12)	2950	v _s CH ₂ (C12)	2956	v _s CH ₂ (C12)
2940vw	2942	v _s CH ₂ (C11)	2946	v _s CH ₂ (C11)	2952	v _s CH ₂ (C11)
	2935	vC10-H20	2936	vC10-H20	2945	vC10-H20
	2921	v _s CH ₃	2919	v _s CH ₃	2924	v _s CH ₃

1560m	1571	ν N8-C15	1538	ν N8-C15	1529	ν N8-C15
1560m	1548	ν C18-C19, ν C16-C17	1528	ν C18-C19, ν C16-C17	1525	ν C16-C17
1468m	1508	ν_a NO ₂	1473	ν C15-C16	1467	ν C18-C19, ν C15-C16
1468m	1469	ν C15-C16	1429	ν_a NO ₂	1427	δ CH ₂ (C13)
1468m	1444	δ CH ₂ (C13)	1418	δ_a CH ₃	1419	ν_a NO ₂
	1437	δ_a CH ₃	1414	δ CH ₂ (C13)	1408	δ_a CH ₃
	1424	δ_a CH ₃	1399	δ_a CH ₃	1389	δ_a CH ₃
1397w	1390	ρ' C10-H20	1383	ρ C10-H20	1383	ρ C10-H20
	1388	δ CH ₂ (C12)	1380	δ CH ₂ (C12)	1376	δ CH ₂ (C12)
	1382	δ CH ₂ (C11)	1372	ν C17-C18	1370	ν C17-C18
	1377	δ CH ₂ (C11)	1367	δ CH ₂ (C11)	1359	δ CH ₂ (C11)
	1354	wagCH ₂ (C13)	1355	ρ C15-H30	1355	ρ C15-H30
	1350	δ_s CH ₃	1352	wagCH ₂ (C13)	1342	wagCH ₂ (C13)
	1343	ν C17-C18	1336	δ_s CH ₃	1334	δ_s CH ₃
1323s	1332	ρ C10-H20	1328	ρ' C10-H20	1332	ρ' C10-H20
1323s	1313	ν_s NO ₂ , ν N9-C19	1312	wagCH ₂ (C12), ρ CH ₂ (C13)	1316	wagCH ₂ (C12), ρ CH ₂ (C13)
1301s	1308	ρ C15-H30	1294	ν N9-C19	1283	ν N9-C19
	1262	wagCH ₂ (C12)	1262	wagCH ₂ (C11)	1264	wagCH ₂ (C11)
1247s	1243	wagCH ₂ (C11)	1251	wagCH ₂ (C11)	1253	wagCH ₂ (C12)
1247s	1231	ν C19-O4	1223	β C18-H32	1212	ν C19-O4
1247s	1221	ν_a SO ₂	1191	ρ CH ₂ (C11)	1190	ν N7-N8
1191m	1190	ν N7-C13	1187	ν C16-O4	1175	ν C16-O4
1191m	1175	ν C16-O4	1175	ν_a SO ₂	1155	ν_a SO ₂
1191m	1173	ν C19-O4	1163	ν_s NO ₂ , ν C16-O4	1150	β C18-H32
1160w	1140	ρ CH ₂ (C11)	1144	ρ CH ₂ (C11)	1124	ρ CH ₂ (C11)
1110vs	1136	ρ CH ₂ (C12)	1138	ρ CH ₂ (C12)	1117	ν_s NO ₂ , ρ CH ₂ (C12)
1110vs	1110	ρ CH ₂ (C13)	1113	ν N7-C10	1112	ν N7-C10
1080s	1065	ν N7-N8	1071	ρ' CH ₃	1069	ρ' CH ₃
	1061	ρ CH ₃	1063	ν N7-C13	1064	ρ CH ₃
1015s	1045	ν_s SO ₂	1023	ν_s SO ₂	1015	ν_s SO ₂
	1005	β C17-H31, β C18-H32	1005	β C17-H31	1007	β C17-H31
	1001	ν C10-C14	998	ν C10-C14	997	ν C10-C14
982m	976	ν C16-C17	972	ν C16-C17, β R ₂ (A2)	960	ν C16-C17, β R ₂ (A2)
	961	β R ₁ (A2)	951	ν C19-O4	944	β R ₁ (A2)
	937	τ_w CH ₂ (C12)	942	ν C13-C12	927	ν C13-C12
	906	ν C13-C12	917	γ C18-H32	922	γ C18-H32
901s	903	γ C18-H32	908	τ_w CH ₂ (C13)	908	τ_w CH ₂ (C13)
	893	wagC15-H30	884	wagC15-H30	891	wagC15-H30
	877	ν C10-C11, ρ' CH ₃	875	ν C10-C11	879	ν C10-C11
851m	844	τ_w CH ₂ (C11)	841	ρ CH ₃	843	τ_w CH ₂ (C11)
851m	822	τ_w CH ₂ (C13)	822	β R ₃ (A1)	824	β R ₃ (A1)
807m	819	δ NO ₂	808	τ_w CH ₂ (C12)	807	τ_w CH ₂ (C12)
807m	808	β R ₂ (A2)	805	δ NO ₂	803	δ NO ₂
807m	806	γ C17-H31	802	γ C17-H31	793	γ C17-H31
729m	728	ν N7-C10	729	ν C11-S1	729	ν C11-S1
	725	wagNO ₂	721	wagNO ₂	717	wagNO ₂

	703	ν C11-S1	704	τ_w CH ₂ (C11)	703	ν C11-S1
664m	662	γ C16-C15	668	τ R ₁ (A2), γ C16-C15	667	γ C16-C15
	616	ν C12-S1	620	ν C12-S1	620	ν C12-S1
	588	β N7-N8	591	β C16-C15	591	ρ NO ₂ , β C16-C15
	573	τ R ₂ (A2)	564	ρ NO ₂	565	ρ NO ₂
567s	563	ρ NO ₂	563	τ R ₂ (A2)	561	τ R ₂ (A2)
520m	539	β R ₁ (A1)	536	β R ₁ (A1)	537	β R ₁ (A1)
520m	502	δ SO ₂	493	δ SO ₂	492	δ SO ₂
	478	ν N9-C19	481	β R ₁ (A2)	486	ν N9-C19
	455	β R ₂ (A1)	455	β R ₂ (A1)	454	β R ₂ (A1), δ N7N8C15
435s	420	ρ SO ₂	414	ρ SO ₂	413	ρ SO ₂
	396	β R ₃ (A1), δ N7C10C14	399	δ N7C10C14	402	δ N7C10C14
	391	β C16-C15	392	β C16-C15	393	τ R ₂ (A1)
	358	τ_w SO ₂	358	τ_w SO ₂	359	τ_w SO ₂
	331	τ R ₁ (A2)	331	τ N8-C15	331	τ N8-C15
	289	τ_w SO ₂	298	τ_w N8-N7	298	τ_w N8-N7
	281	δ C11C10C14	288	δ C11C10C14	288	δ C11C10C14
	279	τ R ₂ (A1)	272	τ R ₂ (A1)	279	τ R ₂ (A1)
	260	β C19-N9	266	ρ NO ₂	266	β C19-N9
	245	wagSO ₂	250	wagSO ₂	251	wagSO ₂
	223	τ_w N8-N7	225	τ_w N8-N7	229	τ_w N8-N7
	203	τ_w CH ₃	195	τ_w CH ₃	212	τ_w CH ₃
	181	γ C19-N9	176	γ C19-N9	176	γ C19-N9
	149	β N7-N8	152	β C19-N9	151	β N7-N8
	122	τ R ₁ (A1)	121	τ R ₁ (A1)	124	τ R ₁ (A1)
	114	τ R ₃ (A1)	113	τ R ₃ (A1)	116	τ R ₂ (A1)
	95	τ N8-C15	100	τ_w NO ₂	104	τ R ₃ (A1)
	63	τ_w NO ₂	61	δ N8C15C16	69	δ N8C15C16
	55	δ N8C15C16, δ N7N8C15	52	δ N7N8C15	55	τ_w NO ₂
	27	γ N7-N8	23	τ_w C15-C16	30	τ_w C15-C16
	22	τ_w C15-C16	17	γ N7-N8	25	γ N7-N8

Note: Abbreviations: ν , stretching; β , deformation in the plane; γ , deformation out of plane; wag, wagging; τ , torsion; ρ , rocking; τ_w , twisting; δ , deformation; a, antisymmetric; s, symmetric; A1, methylthiomorpholine ring; A2, nitrofuran ring; ^aThis work, ^bFrom scaled quantum mechanics force field with B3LYP/6-311++G** method.

Source: ^cFrom Bedogni, et al., 2023.

Then, the antisymmetric and symmetric modes of NO₂ groups are predicted between 1473 and 1117 cm⁻¹, as observed in species containing these groups (Iramain, et al., 2023; Castillo, et al., 2017; Romani, Márquez, & Brandán, 2023) and, for these reasons, these vibration modes are assigned to the intense bands at 1468, 1323, 1191 and 1110 cm⁻¹. On the other hand, the antisymmetric modes of SO₂ groups are

predicted in gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solution at 1247, 1175 and 1155 cm⁻¹, respectively, therefore, they are assigned to the IR bands at 1247 and 1191 cm⁻¹ while the corresponding symmetric modes in the three media are assigned at 1015 cm⁻¹ (Brizuela, et al., 2014).

The rocking modes or in-plane and out-of-plane deformation modes of C18-H32 and C17-H31 groups in the different media are predicted between 1223 and 1005 cm^{-1} and, for this reason, they are assigned to the bands observed in this region.

The CH_3 deformation modes are predicted between 1418 and 1334 cm^{-1} , as observed in species containing these groups (Romani, Márquez, & Brandán, 2023) while the corresponding to CH_2 groups between 1444 and 1359 cm^{-1} . Hence, those vibration modes are assigned in the same regions, as predicted by calculations and, as observed in similar species (Iramain, et al., 2023; Castillo, et al., 2017; Romani, Márquez, & Brandán, 2023; Brizuela, et al., 2014). The CH_3 rocking modes are predicted between 1144 and 1061 cm^{-1} and, for this reason, they are assigned to the bands observed in this region. The wagging and rocking modes of CH_2 groups are predicted by calculations at 1316/1243 and 1191/1110 cm^{-1} , respectively. Hence, they are assigned in the predicted regions, as detailed in Table 11.

1000-10 cm^{-1} region. The deformation, wagging, rocking and twisting modes of NO_2 and SO_2 groups together with CH_2 and CH_3 twisting modes and other skeletal modes are expected in this region. Hence, only the deformation, wagging and rocking modes of NO_2 groups have been assigned at 807, 725 and 563 cm^{-1} , respectively because the twisting modes are

predicted between 100 and 55 cm^{-1} where there are not observed IR bands. Then, the deformation and rocking modes of SO_2 groups are assigned at 520 and 435 cm^{-1} because the wagging and twisting modes in the different media are predicted at 358/359/289 and 245/250/251 cm^{-1} where there are not observed IR bands. Only, the twisting modes of CH_2 groups have been assigned to the band at 851 cm^{-1} while these modes for the CH_3 groups in gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solution are predicted respectively at 203, 195 and 212 cm^{-1} but they are not assigned because the IR spectrum only was recorded until 400 cm^{-1} . The deformations and torsions rings are assigned as predicted by calculations and as reported for similar species (Iramain, et al., 2023; Castillo, et al., 2017; Romani, Márquez, & Brandán, 2023; Brizuela, et al., 2014).

Force Constants

The scaled harmonic force constants have been computed for nifurtimox in the gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solution from the corresponding harmonic force fields calculated by the using 6-311++G** level of theory with the SQMFF methodology and the Molvib program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). The results are summarized in Table 12 and compared with the reported for benznidazole in the gas phase at the same level of theory (Iramain, et al., 2023).

Table 12. Scaled Internal Force Constants for Nifurtimox in Gas Phase, DMSO and Aqueous Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory Compared with Reported for Benznidazole**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method				
Force constants	Nifurtimox ^a			Benznidazole
	Gas phase	DMSO	Water	Gas phase
$f(\nu\text{C-N})$	4.37	4.53	4.60	5.00
$f(\nu\text{C-O})$	5.50	5.45	5.40	
$f(\nu\text{C-C})$	5.16	5.14	5.12	
$f(\nu\text{C-S})$	2.50	2.60	2.65	
$f(\nu\text{N-N})$	6.00	6.30	6.40	
$f(\nu\text{NO}_2)$	9.04	8.16	7.53	9.15
$f(\nu\text{SO}_2)$	8.06	7.51	7.21	
$f(\nu\text{C-H})_R$	5.40	5.35	5.35	5.16
$f(\nu\text{C-H})$	4.85	4.90	4.95	

$f(\nu\text{CH}_3)$	4.87	4.87	4.87	
$f(\nu\text{CH}_2)$	4.86	4.88	4.90	4.90

Note: Units are mdyn \AA^{-1} for stretching.

Source: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Iramain, et al., 2023.

The results for NFX show some differences in the $f(\nu\text{C-N})$, $f(\nu\text{C-S})$, $f(\nu\text{N-N})$ and $f(\nu\text{C-H})$ force constants which evidence higher values in aqueous solution because these constants are associated to the donors groups of H bonds, as revealed by the higher topological properties in aqueous solution by AIM studies. On the other hand, the lower values observed in the $f(\nu\text{C-O})$, $f(\nu\text{NO}_2)$ and $f(\nu\text{SO}_2)$ force constants of nifurtimox in aqueous solution are justified by the higher predicted bond lengths related to the S=O and N-O groups. Besides, the force constants related to the CH_3 groups remains practically constant in the different media although those related to the CH_2 groups change slightly with the medium. The differences observed between the force constants of NFX with the corresponding to benzimidazole are associated to the different structures of these compounds and, hence, to the different rings linked to NO_2 group. Thus, in NFX that group is linked to nitrofurane ring while in benzimidazole to nitroimidazol one.

Electronic Spectrum

The predicted electronic spectrum of NFX in DMSO solution compared with the corresponding experimental in the same medium taken from Bulffer, Castro, & Fanelli, (2011) are shown in Figure 8 by using the TD-DFT method and the B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory. The experimental spectrum showed two bands, one intense absorption at 278 nm and other of lower intensity at 400 nm while the predicted spectrum shows weak bands at 152, 217 and 290 nm with a very strong band and a shoulder at 423 and 190 nm, respectively. The positions and intensities of bands can be seen in Table 13.

Figure 8. Experimental Ultraviolet-Visible Spectrum of NFX in Aqueous Solution Compared with the Corresponding Predicted in DMSO Solution at the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Table 13. TD-DFT Calculated Visible Absorption Wavelengths (nm) for Nifurtimox in DMSO by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory, Compared with the Corresponding Experimental in the Same Medium**

Experimental DMSO	B3LYP/6-311++G**	Assignment
	DMSO	
	152w	$n \rightarrow \sigma^*$
	190sh	
	217w	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
278vs	290m	
400m	423vs	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$

These absorptions can be quickly assigned to $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ interactions, as suggested by NBO calculations due to the presence of C=C and C=N groups among other.

Conclusions

In this study, hybrid B3LYP/6-31G* calculations have been performed on the anti-chagasic nifurtimox agent (NFX) in the gas phase, DMSO and aqueous solution in order to characterize the structures and vibrational spectra of nifurtimox. The calculations have predicted the most stable conformer in agreement with the experimental reported by X-ray diffraction with a solvation energy in aqueous solution higher (-134.81 kJ/mol) than in DMSO solution (-90.71 kJ/mol). In water, the structure presents a higher dipole moment and contraction of volume probably due to the presence of strongly acceptors SO₂ and NO₂ groups of H bonds associated to its higher permittivity of water. The mapped MEP surfaces reveal strong red colours and nucleophilic sites on the SO₂ and NO₂ groups with higher energy value in water. The NBO calculations support the higher stability of NFX in solution while the frontier orbitals suggest that NFX drug is most reactive in both solutions than in the gas phase. Here, complete vibrational assignments of FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra in the three media have been performed by using the normal internal coordinates, the SQMFF methodology and the Molvib program. The harmonic force fields in the three media have been also reported. Good concordances are observed when the predicted NMR and UV-vis spectra are compared with the corresponding experimental ones.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Prof. Tom Sundius for his permission to use MOLVIB.

Author contribution

Maximiliano A. Iramain: Performed the experiments, Analysis tools or data, Contributed reagents.. Karina A. Guzzetti: Performed the experiments, Conceived and designed the experiments. Maria E. Manzur: Contributed reagents, materials. Maria V. Castillo: Contributed reagents, materials. Silvia Antonia

Brandán: Analysed and interpreted the data, Wrote the paper.

Funding

This work was supported with grants from CIUNT Project N°. 26/D714 (Consejo de Investigaciones, Universidad Nacional de Tucumán).

Data availability Available when the authors require it.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Bader, R. F. W. (1990). *Atoms in molecules: A quantum theory*. Oxford University Press.
- Becke, A. D. (1988). Density-functional exchange-energy approximation with correct asymptotic behavior. *Physical Review A*, 38(6), 3098–3100.
<https://doi.org/10.1103/physreva.38.3098>
- Bedogni, G., Arrúa, E., Seremeta, K., Okulik, N., & Salomon, C. (2023). Elucidating the complexation of nifurtimox with cyclodextrins. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 382, 121852.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2023.121852>
- Besler, B. H., Merz, K. M., & Kollman, P. A. (1990). Atomic charges derived from semiempirical methods. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 11(4), 431–439.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.540110404>
- Bezerra, E. M., Bezerra-Neto, J. R., Sales, F. A. M., dos Santos, R. P., Martins, A. M. C., & de Lima-Neto, P. (2014). Optical absorption of the antitrypanocidal drug Benznidazole in water. *Molecules*, 19(4), 4145–4156.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules19044145>
- Biegler-König, F., Schönbohm, J., & Bayles, D. (2001). AIM2000: A program to analyze and visualize atoms in molecules. *Journal of Computational Chemistry*, 22(5), 545–559.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/1096->

Brain-Isasi, S., Quezada, C., Pessoa, H., Morello, A., Kogan, M. J., & Alvarez-Lueje, A. (2008). Determination and characterization of new benzimidazoles with activity against *Trypanosoma cruzi* by UV spectroscopy and HPLC. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 16(16), 7622–7630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2008.07.021>

Brizuela, A. B., Raschi, A. B., Castillo, M. V., Davies, L., Romano, E., & Brandán, S. A. (2014). Vibrational investigation on species derived from cyclamic acid in aqueous solution by using HATR and Raman spectroscopies and SCRF calculations. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1074, 144–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2014.05.019>

Bulffer, R. F., Castro, J. A., & Fanelli, S. L. (2011). Metodología UV para la determinación de los antichagásicos Nifurtimox y Benznidazole en sangre. *Acta Bioquímica Clínica Latinoamericana*, 45(3), 463–470.

Castillo, M. V., Rudyk, R. A., Davies, L., & Brandán, S. A. (2017). Analysis of the structure and the FT-IR and Raman spectra of 2-(4-nitrophenyl)-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one. Comparisons with the chlorinated and methylated derivatives. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1140, 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2016.08.070>

Chaves, O. A., Ferreira, R. C., da Silva, L. S., de Souza, B. C. E., Cesarin-Sobrinho, D., Netto-Ferreira, J. C., Sant'Anna, C. M. R., & Ferreira, A. B. B. (2018). Multiple spectroscopic and theoretical approaches to study the interaction between HSA and the antiparasitic drugs: Benznidazole, metronidazole, nifurtimox, and megalol. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*, 29(7), 1551–1562. <https://doi.org/10.21577/0103-5053.20180029>

Dennington, R. D., Keith, T. A., & Millam, J. M. (2019). *GaussView* (Version 6.1.1). Semichem Inc.

Ditchfield, R. (1974). Self-consistent perturbation theory of diamagnetism. I. A gauge-

invariant LCAO method for NMR chemical shifts. *Molecular Physics*, 27(4), 714–722. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00268977400100711>

Foces-Foces, M. C., Hernandez Cano, F., Claramunt, R. M., Fruchier, A., & Elguero, J. (1988). Molecular structure in the solid state (X-ray diffraction) and in solution (¹H and ¹³C NMR) of Nifurtimox and two pyrazol-1-yl analogs. *Bulletin des Sociétés Chimiques Belges*, 97(11–12), 1147–1157.

Frisch, M. J., Trucks, G. W., Schlegel, H. B., Scuseria, G. E., et al. (2019). *Gaussian 16, Revision C.01*. Gaussian, Inc.

Glendening, E. D., Badenhoop, J. K., Reed, A. D., Carpenter, J. E., & Weinhold, F. (1996). *NBO 3.1*. Theoretical Chemistry Institute, University of Wisconsin.

Iramain, M. A., Manzur, M. E., Castillo, M. V., Checa, M. A., Romano, E., & Brandán, S. A. (2023). Vibrational characterization of active drug to the treatment of Chagas disease, Benznidazole by using force fields and internal coordinates. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(5), 64–92. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).07](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).07)

Keresztury, G., Holly, S., Besenyi, G., Varga, J., Wang, A. Y., & Durig, J. R. (1993). Vibrational spectra of monothiocarbamates-II. IR and Raman spectra, vibrational assignment, conformational analysis and *ab initio* calculations of S-methyl-N,N-dimethylthiocarbamate. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 49(12), 2007–2026. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0584-8539\(09\)91012-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0584-8539(09)91012-1)

Lang, D., Schulz, S. I., Piel, I., Tshitenge, D. T., & Stass, H. (2022). Structural and mechanistic investigation of the unusual metabolism of Nifurtimox. *Chemical Research in Toxicology*, 35(11), 2037–2048. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.2c00210>

Lee, C., Yang, W., & Parr, R. G. (1988). Development of the Colle-Salvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron density. *Physical Review B*, 37(2), 785–789. <https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevb.37.785>

- Maldonado, E., Rojas, D. A., Urbina, F., & Solari, A. (2021). The use of antioxidants as potential co-adjuvants to treat chronic Chagas disease. *Antioxidants*, *10*(7), 1022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10071022>
- Marenich, A. V., Cramer, C. J., & Truhlar, D. G. (2009). Universal solvation model based on solute electron density and a continuum model of the solvent defined by the bulk dielectric constant and atomic surface tensions. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, *113*(18), 6378–6396. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp810292n>
- Miertuš, S., Scrocco, E., & Tomasi, J. (1981). Electrostatic interaction of a solute with a continuum. *Chemical Physics*, *55*(1), 117–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-0104\(81\)85090-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-0104(81)85090-2)
- Moroni, A. B., Perez Mayoral, E., Lionello, D. F., Vega, D. R., Kaufman, T. S., & Calvo, N. L. (2023). Solid-state properties of Nifurtimox: Preparation, analytical characterization, and stability of an amorphous phase. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*, *184*, 25–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2023.01.008>
- Nuñez-Vergara, L. J., Squella, J. A., Aldunate, J., Letelier, M. E., Bollo, S., Repetto, Y., Morello, A., & Spencer, P. L. (1997). Nitro radical anion formation from nifurtimox: Biological evidences in *Trypanosoma cruzi*. *Bioelectrochemistry and Bioenergetics*, *43*, 151–155.
- Parr, R. G., Szentpály, L. V., & Liu, S. (1999). Electrophilicity index. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, *121*(9), 1922–1924. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja983494x>
- Pearson, R. G. (1986). Absolute electronegativity and hardness correlated with molecular orbital theory. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *83*(22), 8440–8441. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.83.22.8440>
- Pulay, P., Fogarasi, G., Pongor, G., Boggs, J. E., & Vargha, A. (1983). Combination of theoretical *ab initio* and experimental information to obtain reliable harmonic force constants: Scaled quantum mechanical (QM) force fields for glyoxal, acrolein, butadiene, formaldehyde, and ethylene. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, *105*(23), 7073–7079. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00362a005>
- Rauhut, G., & Pulay, P. (1995). Transferable scaling factors for density functional derived vibrational force fields. *Journal of Physical Chemistry*, *99*(9), 3093–3100. <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100010a019>
- Romani, D., Márquez, M. J., & Brandán, S. A. (2023). Vibrational study of mono and diprotonated species of potent anti-acid ranitidine hydrochloride combining DFT with SQMFF calculations. *Biointerface Research in Applied Chemistry*, *13*(3), 348. <https://doi.org/10.33263/BRIAC133.248>
- Salah, T., Belaidi, S., & Melkemi, N. (2016). *In silico* investigation by conceptual DFT and molecular docking of antitrypanosomal compounds for understanding cruzain inhibition. *Journal of Theoretical and Computational Chemistry*, *15*(3), 1650021. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219633616500218>
- Soriano-Correa, C., Raya, R., & Esquivé, O. (2008). Characterization of electronic structure and physicochemical properties of antiparasitic Nifurtimox analogues: A theoretical study. *International Journal of Quantum Chemistry*, *108*, 1369–1379. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qua.21707>
- Sperandeo, N. R., Karlsson, A., Cuffini, S., Pagola, S., & Stephens, P. W. (2005). The crystal structure and physicochemical characteristics of 2-hydroxy-N-[3(5)-pyrazolyl]-1,4-naphthoquinone-4-imine, a new antitrypanosomal compound. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, *6*(4), E605–E611. <https://doi.org/10.1208/pt060473>
- Sundius, T. (2002). Scaling of *ab-initio* force fields by MOLVIB. *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, *29*(1), 89–95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2031\(01\)00189-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2031(01)00189-8)
- Terra Martins, F., Ayala, A. P., Porcal, W., Cerecetto, H., González, M., & Ellena, J. (2010). Structural relationships in the solid state of the anti-Chagas agent (E)-phenylethenylbenzofuroxan. *Molecular Diversity*, *14*(4), 643–652. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11030-009-9202-4>

Tomasi, J., & Persico, M. (1994). Molecular interactions in solution: An overview of methods based on continuous distributions of the solvent. *Chemical Reviews*, 94(7), 2027–2094. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr00031a013>

Ugliengo, P. (1998). *MOLDRAW Program*. University of Torino, Dipartimento Chimica IFM.